

ILLUSIVE SCULPTURE THROUGH
ILLUMINATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the impact of projector light and interaction in optical illusion. The elaboration of this topic is realized by merging physical and virtual reality in the form of figurative sculpture. This unification of realities is achieved by replacing natural attributes (texture, colour, etc.) of a physical object with new computer-generated attributes, which are projected on the object. Projected surface that is used in this project is a head sculpture (model) and an additional back screen. The head model will be the main projected surface and will be controlled (rotated) by the audience. Furthermore, in order to have independent visuals for the head model and the screen, the technique of projection mapping is used to map the surface of the head model. Because the audience can rotate the head model, the mapping process of this model is achieved in real-time. The projected scenes that are going to be used will be striking visuals, which in certain points are supposed to mix the awareness of what is real and what is illusion.

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of the project is to project visuals onto a live-mapped complex surface, which is controlled by the audience. Furthermore, achieving visual illusions by combining live-mapped and static-mapped visuals is considered as an additional project goal.

Doing projection mapping in a head model and on a simple flat surface has been the method that is used to accomplish aims of the project. Projection is realised in two surfaces, in order of achieving visual illusion by combining these surfaces. The live element of this project, one of the most important attributes of this research paper, is related to audience interaction. The audience in this project have the possibility to rotate the physical object that is used for projection, which means that the audience will have an input on the projected surface and will influence control on the process of real-time mapping.

The process of achieving the real-time render projection mapping through the audience interaction has required the combination of different work fields. In this paper is explained in detail the workflow of this process, starting with the background information for this project and where the idea came from, before explaining how the mechanics, electronics and programing have been used to accomplish the aim of the project. Furthermore, in this paper is also elaborated the way that visuals are created and what these visuals try to show. At the end of this research paper, are shown the difficulties of this process and what contributions this project can offer in the field of projection mapping.

The project will be considered a success if it manages to give the audience the possibility of controlling the projected surface, and if the projected visuals create the optical illusion of depth and motion.

BACKGROUND

This section of the paper elaborates the ideology behind the project. Human visual perception is clarified in the beginning, by explaining how the pictures are created in brain and how this fact stimulates optical illusion. Second part of this section talk about spatial augmented reality in general and projection mapping in particular as the medium of this reality. Thirdly, audience interaction is elaborated as one of the main characteristics of this project. Final part of this section is reserved to discuss similar projects, by putting the focus on the comparison with this project.

VISUAL PERCEPTION

Vision does not work like camera by just taking pictures and than providing an image report of what it was seen. (Hoffman, 2005). What is seen is not only what is there to be seen but also how the visual system work and interprets images. This system besides transmitting images or signals to the brain also contribute in the way of how these signals are interpreted and organised (Hoffman, *The Interpretation of Visual Illusions*, 1983). Therefore vision dose not show definite truth but shows a complex detective work (Hoffman, *Visual illusions and perception*, 2005).

Retina is layer at the back of the eye, which receives the light and than send this light to the brain in form of signals that brain can understand. (Healthline Editorial Team, 2014). Retina is the place where the complex detective work that was mentioned earlier takes place. Retinal images are unclear therefore these images need that vision system to organise and interpret them. Unclearness of the retinal images is mainly related with the fact that the world is in three-dimensions but the retina is two-dimensional. For realising this images in three-dimensions visual system realise some complex inferences that most of the time are achieved without any awareness (Hoffman, *The Interpretation of Visual Illusions*, 1983).

For example “trading towers” illusion is seen as three-dimensional shape despite the fact that is just a simple two-dimensional flat shape (see Figure 1). Visual system in this case falsely fabricate this shape in three-dimensions even though we know that should be flat. So in this case visual system fabricate the depth of this shape and shows it as a three-dimensional object and does not listen other parts of the brain that challenge it.

Intelligent problem solving based on knowledge has likewise impact in general perception and particularly in visual perception. Illusions can be caused by misapplied or disproportionate knowledge. It was Hermann von Helmholtz who said that perception is indirectly connected with object, constantly interrupted with fragment data by the eyes that are not always relevant and in this case knowledge is used to make sense of the tangible signals. He has defined visual perception as not conscious interpretation from tangible information and knowledge. Based on Herman perception

is similar to prescient hypotheses, but which are shown in outer space and are acknowledged as instant reality (Gregory, 1997).

FIGURE 1: TRADING TOWERS ILLUSION (HOFFMAN, VISUAL ILLUSIONS AND PERCEPTION, 2005).

Besides all the knowledge about ‘illusion’ it is almost impossible to give the right definition. Some may say that is deviation of the reality but even the definition of the reality is almost impossible to be given (Zizek, 2003). Even though there are difficulties to define ‘illusion’, three categories of illusion are very clear. Visual illusions can be categorized as physical, psychological and cognitive illusions. Physical illusions are those illusions that happen before the light enters the eye, so they basically look different from the object that makes them. Psychological illusions are illusions that affect the eyes or brain with stimulation of specific type (colour, size, position, tilt, movement). And cognitive illusions are defined as illusions that interact with different levels of perception to distinguish knowledge of object with general knowledge in order to create misdirection (Sarcone, 2014). Cognitive illusions are those illusions that are used in visualization part of this project.

SPATIAL AUGMENTED REALITY AND PROJECTION MAPPING

Since 1965 when Ivan Southerland introduced the term “Ultimate display” (Owen, 1999) people from research community have been thinking about fully computer-generated world where people would have the possibility to dive in and be part of that world. These ideas have been attached with the notation of virtual environment. In these environments computers control our senses, and our actions affect the computer stimulation. Within the idea of creating virtual environments many researches have been done in different directions, and during these researches AR (Augmented Reality) and VR (Virtual Reality) have been presented as terminologies (Bimler & Raskar, Spatial Augmented Reality Merging Real and Virtual World, 2005). There are many disagreements if VR and AR are parallel fields or one is main category and the other one is subcategory in it. Even though there have been disagreements in classification everyone in research community accept the conclusion that they do things differently, but both of them try to reach almost same result. Main difference of AR with VR is that AR does not try to put us in complete computer generated world, but attempts to bring that computer-generated world in our environment. So in AR

case physical environment plays a central role, which is not true in VR (Bimber & Raskar, 2005).

Augmented reality is extension of physical environment, where attributes of that environment may be influenced or completely changed by an additional computer-generated layer (Glockner, Jannek, Mahn, & Theis, 2014). Augmented reality and real environment have strong spatial link, and in AR community this link is called *registration*. Ivan Sutherland is considered to be the man who has given the first push of augmented reality. Sutherland has designed Head-Mounted-Display (HMD) and this moment is considered to be also the birth of augmented reality (Bimber & Raskar, Spatial Augmented Reality Merging Real and Virtual World, 2005).

Since Head-Mounted-Displays were introduced they have been major technologies for augmented reality. However during the recent years new approaches such as beam split mirrors, transparent screens, holograms and projectors have been pushing the borders of augmented reality. Those methods of augmented reality are classified as Spatial Augmented Reality (SAR). And the fact is that with evolution of SAR many problems of traditional AR have been solved (Bimber & Raskar, Modern approaches to augmented reality, 2006). Projection Mapping, which will be explained later in this section, is part of Spatial Augmented Reality furthermore SAR is a subcategory or special technique of Augmented Reality.

One main benefit of SAR compared to traditional AR is related with HMD, because in SAR case users do not need to use HMD, which give them many advantages like: higher resolution, better field of view, optimal focus, possibility for tracking and better lighting (Bimber & Raskar, Spatial Augmented Reality Merging Real and Virtual World, 2005). SAR has achieved to create augmented reality without HMD by integrating images directly to the user's physical environment not only in their visual environment (Raskar, Welch, & Fuchs, 1998).

Augmented reality images are generated in optical path by augmented reality displays as is shown in Figure 2. These displays are systems that operate with different mechanical, optical and electronic components to achieve image generation. Optics affect how and where images are formed in different displays (plane or complex non-planar surface) (Bimber & Raskar, Modern approaches to augmented reality, 2006).

While there are many augmented reality displays the work for this project is focused on projection-based spatial displays. These forms of displays use projectors to project images directly in the physical object, which means that they do not need to use any image plane or additional surface between the viewer and visual field (optical field). These forms of displays are becoming attractive because they can use large number of pixels over the area and have a possibility for geometric or non-geometric manipulations over these projected pixels (Raskar, Projector-Based Three Dimensional Graphics, 2002). This form of projection has many advantages compared to other displays like unlimited field for projection, great resolution and user friendly.

Beside advantages in this form of projection are introduced also some problems, for example focal points, shadow casting and the impossibility to project in some surfaces (for example if there are two object in row in some parts of second objects). (Bimber & Raskar, Modern approaches to augmented reality, 2006).

FIGURE 2: OPTICAL PATHS FOR DIFFERENT AUGMENTED REALITY DISPLAYS (BIMBER & RASKAR, MODERN APPROACHES TO AUGMENTED REALITY, 2006).

When a specific object is illuminated a viewer sees that object based on the light that is reflected from the object on the retina of their eyes. Based on this fact there is a possibility to change attributes in optical path while the amount of reflected light would stay the same. When the attributes on the optical path are changed also perception for the attributes of the physical object are changed. This indicates that attributes of physical object can be changed or animated only with image-based projection. In this way physical objects can be populated with virtual images. (Raskar, Welch, Low, & Bandyopadhyay, 2001). This process is illustrated in the Figure 3.

This study is focused in projector-based system, which displays correct visuals into specific places of 3D objects. This form of projection is also known as *Projection Mapping*. Projection mapping is a method of projection, which by mapping the light that is emitted can turn a complex surface into a video display (Jones, 2014). Previously this process of mapping the light required many mathematical and physical calculations (Raskar, Projector-Based Three Dimensional Graphics , 2002), but more recently software can perform all the masking (mapping) visuals of irregular screen shapes. In this project Isadora (real time media manipulation software) is used as a mapping application

FIGURE 3: ACHIVING SAME PERCEPTION FOR DIFFERENT SURFACES WITH THE HELP OF IMAGE BASED PROJECTION (RASKAR, WELCH, LOW, & BANDYOPADHYAY, 2001).

AUDIENCE INTERACTION

In the past the phrase audience has been related with observation. However during the recant years this term is not as appropriate as it used to be. Nowadays borders between audience and artist are getting thinner and thinner (Brown, Novak-Leonard, & Gilbride, 2011). In the recent years the idea of audience participation has taken larger importance and because of this trend now in many museums and from many artist audience input is getting more important (Brown & Ratzkin).

In (Brown, Novak-Leonard, & Gilbride, 2011) the audience is divided into receptive and participatory. In the first category are those who are inactive during the performances, i.e. the observing audience. The participatory audience are those members of audience who influence the main performance. Figure 4 has a deeper clarification of these two categories of audience.

With audience interaction participants appreciate and gain better meaning and impact of the experience. (Canada Council for the Arts, 2012). Audience participation is defined as a possibility for audience to interact with the project in physical, spiritual or emotional way and being more than just a simple spectator. This project is presented in colour, textures and shapes. And interaction part has given the opportunity to the audience to be part of the project, by influencing colours textures and shapes that are projected. Being part of the final result appears to be enjoyed and accepted by the audience (Winkler, 2000).

Strongest point of this spatial augmented reality project is related with audience interaction. Audience in this project influence not only the visuals that are projected on the physical object, but they influence also the object itself. With the idea of putting audience in the centre of the project we have developed special method for mapping our physical object.

FIGURE 4: AUDIENCE INVOLVEMENT SPECTRUM (BROWN, NOVAK-LEONARD, & GILBRIDE, 2011).

In this project audience will have two buttons that allow the audience to rotate the physical object, which mean that also projection surface during the interaction will change. But audience during this interaction beside rotating physical object will also affect visuals that are going to be projected. In this project visuals are divided on scenes and in every scene there are special visual attributes that will be affected by user interactions.

SIMILAR PROJECTS

Although projection mapping is new technique of projection, the usage of this technique in the recent years has been quite large. In these years projection mapping has been used in large scale of fields and for different reasons like production, advertising and art (Jones, 2014). Another thing that should be known before analysing similar projects is that the process of creating projection mapping has been changed significantly during the time (Bimber & Raskar, Spatial Augmented Reality Merging Real and Virtual World, 2005).

Yekpare (monolithic) is an example of projection mapping in Istanbul (Haydarpassa train station) in 2010. Concept of the project is to show Istanbul as a metropolitan and multi, cultural city by creating dramatic and artistic scenes in a building, which has a lot of history in his background. Show has been around 15 minutes long and eight scenes developed the concept (Ekim, 2011). For this project authors have used 10 projectors with 15000 Lumen brightens and 24 speakers with 600 and 800w. 3D Max was used as modeling software where authors have created a model of a building. Afterward Cinema 4D and After Effects were used to create motion graphics,

animations and special effects. Mxwendler another visual application was used to transfer images from computer to the surface and add final effects (Ekim, 2011).

FIGURE 5: YEKPARE PROJECTION MAPPING SHOTS FROM SCENE 4 (EKIM, 2011).

If we compare the Yekpare project with this project, even though they are in completely different scales there are some similarities but also many differences. This project is created based on the idea of live mapping and also interaction, attributes that are not included in the Yekpare project. Since in Yekpare mapping is realised one time in 3D Max and then same model was used constantly. Furthermore, in this project audience interaction influence projected visuals. In the other hand software structure is quite similar in both projects. In both projects 3D Max is used for modeling, Cinema 4D for animation and also a final software for projection. Even though in our case final projection software is not just for projection but is also used for live mapping, animation and interaction. Because scales of these two projects are completely different also hardware structure is different. We use only one projector compared to 10 that are used in Yekpare project, and also in this project sound system is not in the same scale. But this project use Arduino with other electronic component as extra hardware parts for realizing interaction and live mapping.

Cyril Diagne has created another project that is quite similar with this project. In this project author does not create exactly projection mapping but he has developed a structure of projecting into an object which is in constant rotation. By using a stepper motor and some other supporting components of stepper motor together with Arduino author has firstly created a turntable. Than Mapmok an open framework mapping software is used to project in physical object. Main problem that Cyril Diagne has faced has been the process of calibrating projection with object (Diagne, 2013).

Essentially project has some similarity with our project, but concepts are different. First of all in this project visuals are fully structured, secondly because of the project scales simple stepper motor was impossible to be used to count rotations, instead an AC motor with higher power was used, so bigger objects we could rotate. Because AC motor was used, rotations of the object are counted with an additional rotary encoder. Thirdly audience interaction is another thing that is used only in this project.

Leviathan a projection-mapping studio from Chicago has developed a project called “Ghost Box” which is fairly similar to this project. They have realized a projection mapping in moving (rotating) physical object by using an illusion technique called Paper’s Ghost. Two projectors are placed in a portable enclosure place and they project into holographic sheets that are in angular positions, from those sheets reflection illuminate the object as shown in Figure 6. Additionally they have provided user control by a tablet or phone (Screenmag, 2013).

Main tools that are used for this project are Autodesk Maya and Adobe After Effects, which are used for creating animations and modeling the physical object. TouchDesigner is used as a final projection mapping software, which control content of projection in real-time this application is considered the core application of the project (KIRN, 2013).

Compared to this project Ghost Box has many similarities, in the concept and how things are realized. Besides that there are also differences, Ghost Box has many advantages compared to this project like the use of two projectors which lead to better luminance cover of physical object, advanced interaction and portative enclosure. But in the other hand in this project users will feel more attached with the project because project is in the same open space without any screen division, also visuals that are shown in this project are more immersive where the users many times may lose the sense of what is real, but in the Ghost Box visuals are always predictable and there is no immersive experience.

FIGURE 6: PROJECTOR SETUP OF GHOST BOX (KIRN, 2013).

PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

PROJECT OVERVIEW

As was noted above, the aim of this project is to project visuals and optical illusion phenomena onto two different mapped surfaces, where one of the surfaces will be live-mapped and the other one will be static-mapped. The live-mapped surface will be realised in a 3D head model and the static-mapping process will be accomplished through a simple flat plane, which will be placed behind the model as a background. Furthermore, the aim of the project is that the live-mapping process to be achieved with audience interaction. Therefore, a turntable was used as a stand for the head model, and the audience had the possibility of controlling (rotating) this turntable. Figure 7 illustrates the project setup.

The head model for this project was created in 3D Max then 3D printed in dark grey. The turntable was bought from Movetech and has a speed of 2rpm (revolutions per minute). This turntable can be rotated CW (clockwise) and CCW (counter-clockwise). It contains an AC Motor, which is supplied by 220-240V and is fused with a 5Amp; the turntable rotations are controlled with a toggle switch. The projector that is used in this in this project is a NEC PE401H and has a brightness of 4000 lumens. Finally, the back-screen that is placed behind the head model has a width of 1170 cm and a height of 878 cm; the distance of the projector from head model is around 250 cm.

FIGURE 7: PROJECT SETUP

CHALLENGES

Based simply on the project description, it is clear that the most valuable part of the project is related to projection mapping in a non-static model (surface). Aside from being the most valuable segment of the project, this was also the most difficult part to accomplish. This is because, as the surface of the projection would change during the rotation of the head model, these changes would also have to determine the projected attribute (projected area) in that surface. A system that would constantly update the

projectors projection surface based on the outer (physical) conditions of the head model was necessary in this case.

Mapping the head model was another challenge that was related with the process of live mapping. Because of the head structure complexity mapping the head model in a traditional mapping strategy where the surface is mapped by drawing the borders of the surface just with lines and making the use the inner part of the borders for projection was almost impossible. With this strategy around 360 mappings of the same model would need to be realised, and taking into account the complexity of mapping just one of this surfaces this process would be very difficult. But the solution was simplified after being introduced to Isadora (real time media manipulation software). In short, this software provides the possibility of adding 3D models, then manipulating them (i.e. change textures, rotate etc.) and than rendering and projecting the models lives.

HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The hardware implementation in this project is mostly related to mechanics. Mechanical work has been carried out when the head model and electronic components were attached to the turntable with the purpose of achieving communication between turntable and computer. One of the biggest challenges during the implementation was to obtain the values of the turntable rotation. The solution was achieved with an optical rotary encoder, while the solution was not immediately attained. In the section of problems and difficulties, are explained other ways in which this problem was approached.

FIGURE 8: (a) ROTARY ENCODER METHODOLOGY SETUP, (b) PHASE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TWO LIGHT DETECTOR WHICH DETERMINES DIRECTION OF THE ROTATION, (c) ROTARY ENCODER BEARING ASSEMBLY AND SHAFT POSITION

An ‘optical rotary encoder’ is an electronic component, which measures angular positions. These encoders come in two types: an absolute rotary encoder and incremental rotary encoder; for this project an incremental rotary encoder has been used. Optical rotary encoders basically consist of a light source (LED) and a light detector (photo sensor). Between the light source and the light detector is an encoder disc (slotted disc), which when rotated will either allow the light to pass or not to

pass, as is shown in Figure 8 (a). When the encoder is rotated, encoder disc will also be rotated and this rotation will influence the light sensor to generate sequential pulses. However, it should be noted that each encoder has different pulse rates. The encoder that was used in this project generates 1024 pulses per rotation (p/r) but, because it is a quadrature, those pulses are extended to 4096. Then, based on the pulses that the light detector will receive, the encoder will keep track of the angular rotation. Based on this logic, only rotations will be detected and not the direction of the rotation. Therefore, two light sources and two light detectors are used, which are placed in 90 electrical degrees out of phase. Thus, direction is determined based on the phase relationship between the two light detectors (see Figure 8 (b)) (Robopedia, 2014). The bearing assembly of optical rotary encoders was also important for this project. As is shown in Figure 8 (c), a rotary encoder is made of a metallic bearing assembly and, in the middle, is a shaft. This shaft is the bit of the encoder that controls the rotation of the encoder disc, based on the rotations that are applied to it.

After choosing the right component, the challenge was how and where to mount the encoder on the turntable. Based on the idea of using the turntable -- which is made from two plates where one can be rotated and the other one is static -- as a stand, the encoder shaft would ideally be mounted in the centre of the rotary plate. However, as is shown in Figure 9, the turntable that was used in this project has a different structure compared to an ideal one. In short, a screw was placed in the exact spot where the rotary encoder would need to be placed. This screw was holding the rotary plate and was placed in a grub screw, which was glued with the rotary plate and upper bearing of the turntable. Therefore, it was impossible to place the encoder in the spot that was originally planned.

FIGURE 9: B200 MOOVETECH TURNTABLE

The solution was to place the encoder somewhere else on the plate, while finding the correct spot required many experiments. Finally, the decision was to create an

additional plate, and place it above the first one. The plate was created with a diameter of 40cm and another path-hole with a thickness of 3cm was also created on the bottom of the new plate (see Figure 10 (a)). This path-hole was used as an encoder-shaft path during the plate rotations. However, in order to fit the encoder shaft in this path, a wheel for the encoder shaft was created. This wheel had a diameter of 2.5cm and the outer part of the wheel was made from rubber so that it had a better (non-slip) friction surface. The idea was to put the encoder wheel on one side of the turntable plate path-hole so that, when the plate rotates, friction is created between plate and the shaft wheel and this friction will then be converted into shaft rotation based on plate rotation.

The encoder should be mounted under the turntable plate and the wheel-shaft of the encoder should be inserted in the path-hole of the plate. Therefore, an assembly bracket with a threaded lead-screw was bought then modified to hold the encoder (see Figure 10 (b)). The fixing clamp of this assembly bracket was attached to the static (bottom) part of the turntable and then, on the upper part of the assembly bracket, the encoder was attached. Using this technique, it was possible to adjust the exact place where the encoder shaft should be placed on the turntable plate path-hole. Having mounted the incremental rotary encoder in the right place, the process was ready to continue with software implementation.

FIGURE 10: (a) PLATE WITH PATH-HOLE AND DIMENSIONS, (b) ENCODER MOUNTING ASSEMBLY BRACKET

SOFTWARE AND ELECTRONIC IMPLEMENTATION

Different electronic components were used in order to realise the aims of allowing audience interaction and of obtaining the adequate data for the corresponding projection surface. Furthermore, all of the electronic components were required to have communication with a computer in order to control and observe physical behaviours from the computer. Arduino, an electronic open-source physical prototyping platform, was used to control the physical behaviours of electronic and non-electronic hardware (Introduction, 2014). Finally, the software side of the Arduino microcontroller which is based on C and C++ languages and makes it a very comfortable platform was used to write programming code.

COMMUNICATION WITH ROTARY ENCODER

After attaching the incremental rotary encoder to the turntable plate (which is described in the previous section), the goal was to obtain data from the encoder. Therefore, a connection between the encoder and the Arduino Uno was necessary at this point. First, the Arduino was connected to a computer through a USB cable. Then, based on the datasheet of the encoder which is shown in Figure 11 the encoder was connected with the Arduino. In the specifications of the rotary encoder it is stated that the encoder needs a power supply of 5-12 VDC, this was suitable for controlling directly with Arduino. The electronic connection of this component was pretty straightforward. It was achieved by connecting the encoder with the 5V and the 'ground' of the Arduino and then the interrupt pins (2 and 3) with the outputs of the encoder. When the connection was finished, it was time to write the controlling code.

FIGURE 11: DATASHEET FOR INCREMENTAL ROTARY ENCODER (A6B2-CWZ3E-1024)

For this component, an encoder library by Paul Stoffregen was used. Then, in the code the values from the encoder outputs were taken. However, as was noted above, this encoder generates 4096 pulses per revolution but this project needed just 360 so that the mapping surface can be changed every one-degree. Therefore, the total number of pulses (4096) was divided with 360; the result was 11.3777778. This number was then used to divide the incoming values of the encoder. Dealing with aspect ratio of the turntable plate and encoder wheel was another point, because the encoder wheel was much smaller than the turntable plate (inner part) one full rotation of the plate would cause 12 rotations of the wheel ($30/2.5 = 12$). Therefore the values were divided again this time by 12.

Now, the incremental rotary encoder counts the position changes infinitely, for example, after one revolution is finished with 360 it will continue counting with 361, 362 etc. Therefore, in the software it was specified that, when the counting of the impulses is equal to 360 or -360 (CCW), counting should be restarted and continue from zero. Finally, through using a serial monitor it is possible to see the values of the encoder rotations. However, even though it was possible to get the values of the rotation on the computer, the problem was that the Arduino and the computer were connected via a USB cable, which would both limit the performer's range of action and would increase the risk of accident during the performance. Therefore, this

connection was unsuitable for the project and a Bluetooth connection was implemented instead.

BLUETOOTH CONNECTION

For achieving the serial communication Arduino-computer, a JY-MCU Bluetooth module was used. This module has four pins: two of which are for powering (VCC and ground) while the two other pins are for communication (one of them is used as receiver and the other one as transmitter). So connecting this module with Arduino was simple. The VCC was connected to the 5V and ground with ground, and then the receiver of the module was connected with the transmitter of the Arduino (pin 1) and the receiver of Arduino (pin 0) with the transmitter of the Bluetooth module. However, it should be noted that pin 1 and pin 0 in Arduino Uno are the only two pins that are reserved: as transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX).

After connecting the module with the Arduino, the next task was to pair the Arduino with the computer. Here it is worth mentioning that in different computer operating systems the process of pairing that computer with the Arduino through Bluetooth will also be different. The computer that is used in this project uses Mac OS X, so the procedure that is described here stands only for this OS. The first step of pairing after connecting module and Arduino was to connect Arduino and computer through USB (the module then started to blink, which means that the electronics are connected in the correct way). Under the 'Bluetooth Preferences', the Bluetooth module was shown and was asking for pairing permission, before pairing the module pin should be entered (in this case it was 1234, but it can also be 0000). Following that, using the code that was written earlier for the encoder we just added Software Serial library and the code was ready. Before testing however, it was necessary to supply the Arduino with power supply, because, now that a USB cable was not going to be used, the Arduino was without power source. For this purpose a 9VDC adapter was used. Finally, during the test, even though the USB cable was unplugged, values from the encoder rotation were arriving in the serial monitor, this time via Bluetooth.

IMPLEMENTATION OF AUDIENCE INTERACTION

When everything was finished in terms of the encoder, the following step was to give the audience the possibility of controlling the rotations of the turntable (projection surface). Therefore, it was necessary to control the AC motor of the turntable. However, the challenge in this case was that AC motors are not easy and safe to be controlled, especially if they use high voltages as in this case (220-240VAC). The Arduino was used to control this motor, but because Arduino can control only low voltage DC components, a relay was also used.

Relays are electromagnetic switches that with low electronic voltages can switch much larger electric currents. Relays consist of two basic mechanical parts: contacts and an electromagnet (a coil which, under a specific voltage, becomes a magnet). Contacts can be considered as a pair of metal surfaces, which in contact with each

other, allows current to flow in that terminal while if the two contacts are separated (not in contact) than that terminal is off (see Figure 12 (a)). The electromagnet coil controls these contacts in terms of whether they are opened or closed. If a current is applied to the coil, an electromagnetic field is created and this field will cause one of the contacts to move. The terminal is thus closed and electricity can flow. In contrast, if the coil is without electricity the contacts will stay open, because ‘open contacts’ are set as default (see Figure 12 (b)). Basically, by applying or not applying a specific voltage to the coil relays can switch electric components that have much larger currents (Lazaridis, 2010).

FIGURE 12: (a-I) CONTACT CLOSED AND CURRENT CAN NOT FLOW, (a -II) CONTACT OPEN AND CURRENT CAN FLOW, (b-I) WHEN CURRENT IS APPLIED IN COIL, (b -II) WHEN THERE IS NO CURRENT IN COIL

While there are different types of relays, for this project Single Pole Double Through (SPDT) relays were used. This kind of relay will receive one input of the voltage and will then ‘relay’ that current to one of the two outputs. Thus, with this type of relay, both NO and NC contacts can produce the current. SPDT relays are used in this project because there is not a relay that has three outputs. Since the turntable that is used in the project has a circuit, which needs to switch among three terminals (clockwise, counter clockwise and no rotation), a combination of two relays has been used to achieve the right result. One of the relays will be responsible for sending or not sending current to the input (common) of the second relay, and the second relay will produce a current for one of the rotations (CW or CCW), as is shown in Figure 13(a). Finally, for this project, the relays needed to accept a switching voltage 240VAC with current of 5Amp and the coil voltage had to be DC in order for them to be used with the Arduino. Therefore, in order to achieve such a connection a relay shield compatible with Arduino Uno was used.

This shield has four mounted relays each of which had a switching power of 250VAC and a current of 7Amp and needed a power of 5 VDC. By using this shield, security meters were increased significantly and, by extension, the work was simplified. This is because, with this shield, there was no need to use any other additional components (such as transistor and resistor), nor do any soldering, because the shield was mounted in a board and ready for use. Next, as is shown in the figure 13 (b), the main power of the turntable was connected with the ‘common’ of relay number 3, then the ‘NO’ of relay number 3 with the ‘Common’ of relay number 4 and, from this relay, NO and NC were connected with the AC motor. Thus, if the voltage is applied in the first

relay and then the contact in this relay is closed, the voltage will flow in the second relay. The contact of the second relay would be open to begin with, which means that the turntable would start rotating in CCW; then if the contacts of the second relay is closed, the turntable would rotate CW. However, if the first relay stays open then whether the second relay is open *or* closed, the turntable will not rotate, because there will be no current in the second relay. In addition, the impossibility for the second relay to output energy in both NO and NC simultaneously, is one of the factors for using this schematic the relays, because if both NO and NC would output energy in any given situation, the AC motor and the complete circuit would be damaged, potentially leading to injuries. Two buttons have been used for controlling when to open and when to close the contacts of the both relays.

FIGURE 13: (a) SCHEMATIC OF CONNECTING TWO RELAYS, (b) CONNECTING RELAYS IN SEEDSTUDIO SHIELD

With these buttons the audience will have the opportunity to control the relays, and, by extension, to also control the turntable rotations. Basically, as noted above, in the beginning the relay contacts will be open, so by pushing the first button these contacts will close and then the energy will exit through the NO pin of the second relay. Then, if the second button is pushed, the programming code of the Arduino will close both relays; so now the energy will flow from the first relay and will exit in the NC pin of the second relay.

Connecting buttons with the Arduino is simple and requires the use of three of the four pins that the buttons have. One button pin is connected with the ground; the next one is connected with the 5V through a 10K ohm resistor and the last pin with one of the digital pins (9 for one button and 11 for next the other button). Arduino is used to control these two pins and also the two pins that are for controlling the relays of the shield (pin 5 for relay number 3 and pin 4 for relay number 4). Basically within the code, it is ‘written’ (as was noted above) that the first button would close the first relay and the second button will close both relays.

After finishing this communication of turntable-computer through Arduino, the audience would be able to rotate the turntable and the values of the rotation will be

shown in the computer (serial communication). As we have shown, this connection was realised through Bluetooth. However, for completing the desired goal, one more process had to be realised in the software implementation. That is, sending the turntable rotation values to Isadora from Arduino.

ARDUINO-ISADORA SERIAL COMMUNICATION

As was noted above, Isadora is the final mapping software and Isadora, in this project, is responsible for changing the projection-mapping surface. The head model object that was previously 3D printed is imported in Isadora, then in order to realise the projection mapping, the content of the visuals was shown inside that 3D model. Changes of the projection surface are achieved by rotating the head model. This rotation of the head model in Isadora needed to be controlled by the rotation of the turntable and the physical head model. Therefore, it was necessary to have serial communication between Isadora and Arduino, because, until this point, the values of the turntable rotations were going in Arduino through the serial port. For achieving this communication some simple modification of code were done in Arduino and than some configurations were made in Isadora.

In Arduino a line of code (`Serial.print(1,DEC)`) was added, which is used to identify the serial communication and also to specify the data type of the identification. For example, in this case, 1 is used as serial identification and the data type of 1 is DEC. Following that, the data type of the values that the encoder will send in Isadora was specified, this was also DEC. Therefore, in the code line where the rotary encoder values are added in serial ports, we just added DEC after a coma. Having completed everything with Arduino, Isadora was opened.

In Isadora a building block called 'Serial in Watcher' was added. This block needed to obtain the values of the Arduino serial communication and than output that value. Serial in Watcher does not have a ready output section, so this output was added with two lines of code inside this building block: in the first line the number that identifies serial communication with Arduino was added, which is 1 as in Arduino, and the data type was written in the second line. Then, in Serial Port Setup, a serial communication was chosen (Bluetooth communication, which was recognised by the name of the Bluetooth module). Finally, all that was required was to enable this serial communication and, when the turntable was rotating, the output values of the Serial in Watcher were corresponding with the rotation. Thus, by just connecting this output value of Serial in Watcher with the 3D model rotation, it was possible to achieve live render projection mapping.

STARTING/RESTARTING POINT

As was noted above, during audience interaction the head model rotation was realised, and the rotary encoder was used to keep track of the rotation. However, the problem was that, when the system was restarted, the rotary encoder would lose all the data and would start to keep track of the rotation from the beginning. For instance,

if the project was used one time and audience interaction was realised, the head model would end up with a high possibility of not stopping in the same position as when it started. Therefore, the next time the project is used the head could be in a different position, and the rotary encoder will recognise that position as the first one. However, 'first position' in the calibration is defined as static (front of the head), so now the calibration would not be accurate (displaced), and, during the model rotation, the projection would likely be out of sync. Therefore, it was necessary to have a static starting position, in order to ensure correct calibration of projection.

This starting point was realised through a magnet, a magnetic hall sensor and a button. 'Hall effect sensors' convert magnetic fields into electric signals for processing. These sensors are activated by an external magnetic field, and they respond to a wide range of positive and negative magnetic fields. In addition, the output of the sensor is dependent on the density of the magnetic field around the sensor, so if the flux density of the magnetic field passes a certain amount, the sensor will generate a proportional voltage (Storr, 2014).

The A1120EUA-T Hall effect sensor is used for this project. This sensor has three pins one of which is connected with 5V another is connected to the ground and the last is connected with analogue pin 0. As with most of the hall sensors, this sensor -- in cases where there is no magnetic field will output half of the supplied voltage. For example, if we supply 5V to the sensor it will produce 2.5V when there is no magnetic field. And, based on the datasheet, the output when there is magnetic field drops from 2.5mV/Gauss (unit for measuring magnetic field) to 0V or rises to 5V, according to the polarity. This means that 2.5mV for this sensor is equal to 1 Gauss and 1024 analog steps are equal to 5V (because this sensor needs a 5V input). Therefore, 1 step is equal to 1953 mG. To make the output more reliable (i.e. when there is no magnetic field no voltage is produced), the analog output without magnetic field applied was measured which in this case was 508 while it is known that the maximum analogue output is 1024. Then, the value of 508 that was to be subtracted from the analogue output constantly was written into the code. Next, this number was multiplied by 1953mG (as explained earlier) and the result was divided by 1000. Using this method, it was possible to adjust the scale to Gauss.

Furthermore, a magnet was placed underneath the turntable plate, so that when the turntable rotates the sensor will also rotate and the position of the magnet will be used as a starting position. Then, in a static place under the turntable plate, a sensor was placed. When the turntable rotates with the magnet once per rotation, the sensor will be able to read the values of the magnet provided there is not much distance between magnet and the sensor. When the sensor and the magnet were in a straight direction to each other (i.e. the smallest distance), the sensor was outputting a value of around 1800 G (because the sensor is not precisely accurate). Therefore, having attached the button, it was written into the code that, when this button is clicked and the gauss value is smaller than 1800, the turntable should be rotated until this value is 1800 or more. Thus, it was decided that each time the project was used, either immediately

after use or before it was started, the position would be restarted by simply clicking the button, which was placed near the turntable.

VISUALS

In projection mapping, visualisation is considered as the most important element. Even though the process of live mapping is the most valuable research achieved in this project, visuals, as the medium that directly influence the audience, have a huge impact. The visuals of this project are divided into scenes, where each scene has a different time length and different meaning. Cinema 4D and Isadora are two software platforms that were used to realise the visuals. Cinema 4D is a 3D graphic software (modelling, animation and rendering) and, in this project, was used to create the back screen visuals for some of the scenes. Isadora is a real-time media manipulation software where, in contrast to Cinema 4D, all renderings are done live. For example, if the visuals of the back screen for a scene are created in Cinema 4D, these visuals would have to be rendered and saved as a video, which means that all the attributes were static. Then, this video was passed through Isadora where, during the performance, the attributes of the video could be influenced even though the video was created in a different application. Therefore, Isadora was used not only to create visuals but also as the final projection software.

STORYBOARD

Creating a storyboard was the first thing that was completed in order to achieve good visuals. However, it should be noted, that in the end this storyboard was not implemented exactly because, originally, there was not enough knowledge regards to what can be achieved with Isadora. This storyboard is divided in four stages and in this section these stages are elaborated with the help of some illustrated figures.

FIGURE 14: BEGINING OF THE PERFORMANCE – STORYBOARD

Figure 14 illustrates the storyboard of the first stage. This stage is created around the idea of giving the audience the feeling of the projected space, where simple geometric objects (mostly circles) are used to define the borders of the projected space. The scene that follows the first scene simulates the visuals of some doors being opened, and in the inner space of these doors is a snowing. The idea is to give the audience the

feeling that they are ‘getting inside’ the performance. This scene is used as a bridge between simple projection and a projection mapping.

FIGURE 15: BEGANING OF THE HEAD APPERENCE – STORYBOARD

Figure 15 shows three images from the storyboard of the second stage, this is the stage when the projection mapping will start (because before it was just flat projection without mapping). This stage continues with the snow visuals from the last stage, but now the snow falls in a narrower width, or, to be more precise, in the same width as the head model. From this falling snow, the head model will gradually start to have a separate projection (mapping will start). First the head model will be wrapped with visuals in his full width, than it will continue to be wrapped in full height until a complete model is projected.

FIGURE 16: DIFFERENT SCENES WITH DEPTH OPTICAL ILUSION – STORYBOARD

Stage three of the storyboard is shown in Figure 16. In this stage more optical illusions and immersive visuals are simulated. The depth of the field is one of the most used forms of optical illusion and that is stimulated in this performance. As is shown in the above figures, depth will be created in the back-screen, which when shown in combination with the head will provide a more adequate perspective.

FIGURE 17: CLOSING OF THE PERFORMANCE – STORYBOARD

Figure 17 illustrates the closing stage of the storyboard. In this stage, the idea of evolving from one scene to the other one is also shown. The closing scene will be created around the idea of optical illusion, where in the back screen the wall corner

will be projected, which will move in x-axis and y-axis. This scene is followed by a scene, which simulates opening doors as in the beginning. However in this stage the scene will be in reverse: the snow will be falling and then the doors will get closed.

VISUAL DEVELOPMENT

Even though the 3D head model was not originally created but was bought from a 3D artist there were bits on the model that needed intervention. The head model was originally created in 3DS Max. Therefore, the first step was to convert this model from Max to Cinema 4D. Even though there are file types that support both Max and Cinema (like fbx and obj) not every attribute of the file is fully supported. After many unsuccessful tries, only the model without any texture or any special effect was eventually exported from Max in obj format. This file was then imported in Cinema 4D while it was only a blank model. Next, textures were added manually onto the model and some minor changes were made, such as cutting the edges filling and the polygons.

FIGURE 18: ISADORA ACTORS AND THE CONNECTIONS THAT ARE USED TO SHOW THE HEAD MODEL AND TO GIVE THE AUDIENCE ‘INTERACTION’ IN ROTATING IT.

In order to use this model in Isadora, the file was saved as a 3DS file with texture map attached to it. Therefore, the model that was in Cinema 4D needed to be ‘texture-baked’ first. After importing the model in Isadora, a 3D Player actor was used to hold and render the model. Some attributes were changed with regards to the actor, such as the value of z-translate, lighting and render back. When this actor was ready it was connected with a 3D Renderer in order to achieve a full capacity of intervention on the model and, eventually, it was connected with an actor named Projector, so the model could be shown in the screen. The last step was to connect the actor that was explained above (in the section Arduino-Isadora serial communication) Serial In Watcher – Text with y-rotation of the 3D Player actor. This connection was used to

control rotations of the model in the y-axis, based on the data that are passed through serial communication (Arduino). Figure 18 illustrates connections that were completed in Isadora in order to have the 3D head model in the view scene.

The first scene contains visualisation only for the back screen, without any separate visuals for the head model. Not using separate visuals is mentioned because the visuals that are supposed to be projected in the back screen will also be projected in the head model, and the head model stands in between projector and the back screen. This scene is fully created in Cinema 4D because, with this application, the animation can have more exact control when compared to the Isadora. This scene uses only simple geometric objects and tends to use the margins of the projection space.

FIGURE 19: FIRST SCENE WITH SIMEPLE GEOMETRY OBJECTS AND SPACE MARGINS

In Cinema 4D two flat surfaces (planes) were originally created. These planes were placed near each other so they appeared as one flat surface, which was then used as the main surface of the back screen for this scene. Then, in the same dimension of the two planes (plane 1 + plane 2), another big plane was created. This plane was populated with simple circles and was then placed behind the two main planes that were previously created. Having applied the right textures (black for the two planes and luminous white for the circles), the circles were animated to move in z-axis so that they were fading in and out of the scene. In addition, the inner and outer radiuses of the circles were animated. After the circle animation was finished, four other cubes were created and placed in the four sides of the main plates. The Cubes were applied with the same white luminous colour as the circles. These cubes were animated to 'grow' along the border paths of the two main planes like shiny white lines. Figure 19 shows how this animation looked after the work in Cinema 4D was completed. Finally, when the work in Cinema 4D and the animation was rendered (saved as a video), the video was imported in Isadora.

The second scene was created by using both Isadora and Cinema 4D. This scene is a continuation of the first scene and the main plates that were created in the above scene are used also in this scene. However, these two plates were now animated in the way that simulates the idea of two big doors being opened (see figure 20). This animation was the last part of the scene that needed Cinema 4D. Furthermore, by using an actor named 3D Particles, which create particles in a three dimensional system and

manipulate these articles with x, y and z inputs, a Picture Player actor a snow-like video was created in Isadora. This video was then recorded in order to offer the possibility of using simple video and not 3D Particles, because of the memory use that is required by this actor. Next, this video and the video that was created earlier in Cinema 4D for this scene were imported in Isadora and, by using two Movie Player actors and two Projector actors, these videos were combined to be shown in a specific time; more precisely, when the doors of the first video start to open, the snow-like video will start playing. In order to merge these two videos precisely, another actor (named Comparator) was used. This actor controls the length of the video and then, at a specific time, sends a trigger. This trigger was used to start the second video. In addition, attributes of the Projector actor were also manipulated to achieve a perfect combination between these two videos.

FIGURE 20: SECOND SCENE WITH THE VIDEO, WHICH LOOKS LIKE THE DOORS ARE OPENING, AND A SNOW

The two scenes explained thus far are simple projection scenes without any mapping. In the third scene mapping process is introduced and the head model will start to have separate visuals from the back screen. This will continue from the previous scene and the snow effect that is used in the last scene will start narrowing down until it reaches the same width as the head model.

FIGURE 21: SCENE NUMBER THREE BEGINNING OF PROJECTION MAPPING

The head model will use a separate Movie Player with the snow-like video playing, but this video will use also an actor named Dither. With this actor ‘dither’ is added to the video until it no longer appears to be snowing but appears to look like big squares,

which are shown and hidden in turn. Also the so-called 'Shape' actor was used to control places that are going to be projected in the head. The squares will now start to appear slowly, from the top of the head model to the bottom. This gives the idea that the snow is wrapping the head model and is creating a mapping. At this time the snow-like video in the background will remain the same and the width will still be the same as the head model. Figure 21 shows how scene number three looks. When the complete head is wrapped with visuals, the back screen will start to grow in width and the next scene will continue from here.

FIGURE 22: SCENE NUMBER FOUR WITH THE ILLUSION OF WRAPPING

The fourth scene, as with the other scenes, will continue from the previous scene in order to maintain the flow of the visuals. This scene uses the actors from scene number three but also has additional actors: Bloom, Colorizer, Glow and LumaKey. When the back screen 'snow-like' video is in full width, Bloom and Colorizer will give the video a 'shiny bloom effect' and the colours of the snow will change according to the model rotations. When the bloom effect reaches its peak, the snow-like video is replaced with another video, which has been created earlier with particles and then recorded in Isadora (as with the snow-like video explained above). In this video, particles -- which are simple geometric objects -- are fired across the z-axis. Thus, when this video is used in the performance it is now noticeable how the objects flow with depth through the creation of a simple optical illusion that is produced by interfering in the visuals of the head model (because they move in the z-axis sometimes these geometric objects are projected in the head model). Meanwhile, Glow, LumaKey and an additional Dither are used for the head model visuals. These actors create different visuals in the head model but always keep the simple geometries in the centre of the visualisation. At the end of the scene, the texture map of the head model also changes to a wireframe, which gives the head an abstract look as is shown in figure 22 (b). The main idea of this scene is to show projection mapping, which in this scene is, for the most part, achieved by using the idea of wrapping (where visuals are not only projected straight but they are animated to create the illusion of wrapping).

Scene number five has some unique characteristics compared to the other scenes. In this scene head model visuals are created in point texture map, so even when

visualisation is applied to the head model only *the points* will attain texture. The textures that are used for the head model in this scene are mostly just simple animated colours that are controlled by audience interaction through the actor named Zoomer, which moves the colours of the head model.

The back screen, on the other hand, is created around the idea of an audience-controlled optical illusion. Even though the effect of this optical illusion is not that strong, the key to this scene is the idea of audience interaction. This idea is achieved by using two actors called HalfTone. These actors create imagery through continuous tones and through the use of different geometric shapes with different spacing and different sizes. Thus, when combining this effect twice and using different attributes for both of the actors, simple optical illusion effects are created. Movements of the head in this scene are created to stimulate the optical illusion by making the impossible possible. The idea of the head model movements is to make the audience wonder whether the real head is really moving or not. Figure 23 illustrates the point-drawn mode of the head model and also the movement of the model.

FIGURE 23: SCENE NUMBER FIVE, WITH POINT TEXTURE MAP AND HEAD MOVMENT

In the sixth scene, a deep optical illusion is introduced into the performance. This illusion is simulated in the back screen by using 3D Quad Distort actors instead of the simple Projectors. 3D Quad Distorts display a video stream on the 3D plane and the corners of this plane can be distorted (this actor is usually used for mapping planar surfaces). For this performance, five 3D Quad Distorts are used: one as a front surface, two for top and bottom and two for left and right. Next, the four corners of each quad (x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), (x_3, y_3), (x_4, y_4) are manipulated in order to make these quads move in space in a way that will create an illusion of depth. Figure 24 illustrates this process and also shows the values of each quad point in space. As is shown in the figure 24 (a) all the points are 22, this is because every point is independent and the default position of each point for full width and height -- after some manipulation in z-axis -- translate as 22. For example, if the point x_1 moves to the right side, the values will be reduced until they reach -222 and then x_1 will be in

the same position as x_2 . Similarly, if we move x_2 in the left side, the values can be reduced until they reach -222 and x_2 is in the same position as x_1 .

FIGURE 24: IDEA BEHIND 3D QUAD DISTORT AND THE EXACT VALUES THAT ARE APPLIED ON THEM

After defining the 3D Quad Distort actors and by using another HalfTone actor, the visuals for the back screen are created. As is shown in figure 25, the bottom quad distort is not used in this scene to give the idea of the separate floor. This scene will, at first, start with just the left wall fading in and out before the right wall appears. Eventually the front and the top quads will appear in the visuals. By using this method, the audience will see the process in which the depth illusion is built and not only the final result, which is said to affect the optical illusion strength.

FIGURE 25: SIXTH SCENE INTRODUCING DEPTH ILLUSION

The following scene continues with the exact same background visuals but in this scene the head model will also start to appear. In this scene the head model will have an exact human texture, so as to provide the audience with the perception of a real human. This texture is fully created in 3DS Max while in Isadora we do not apply any extra texture. To begin with the head model uses an actor named Explode who ‘disintegrates’ the source texture by dividing it into small chunks. With this actor, the head will be just like a dust to begin with, until it slowly starts to take the shape of the head model. At first, the model will look like it is ‘deeper’ in the space (z-axis

translate) before it adopts its final position. Figure 26 illustrates how the model looks when the Explode actor is used and also how it looks during the movement in z-axis.

FIGURE 26: SCENE NUMBER SEVEN HEAD SHOWING THROUGH EXPLODE ACTOR AND MOVMENT IN THE DEPTH OF FIELD

Scene number eight again uses 3D Quad Distort actors to create depth. In this scene both bottom and top quads are not used, the reason related to the visuals that are projected. Visuals that are created in this scene are of a circular shape and are not applied in full width and height, which means that the edges of the quad distorts will not have any visuals. Thus the point of depth will be eliminated. Therefore, by letting the top and bottom quads assume only a black colour the original field of depth was retained.

FIGURE 27: EIGHTH NUMBER SEVEN AND THE USE OF KALEIDOSCOPE

The visuals of this scene have a major actor called Kaleidoscope and this actor uses the idea of the kaleidoscope cylinder with many mirrors which create reflections. Contrary to usual kaleidoscopes, for the sake of simplicity only two colours were reflected in this performance (kaleidoscopes are known for reflecting many colours), while the audience controls the colour that is displayed through the model rotation. Converting the video into two-tone after using the Kaleidoscope actor was achieved by using another actor called Threshold, who can turn any video input into a two-colour video. In addition, an actor named Colorizer was used to give the audience the possibility to control the colours that are going to be projected. The process that was

mentioned earlier is used to create the visuals for both the back screen and head model. However, because the surfaces are different, the visuals do not seem to be the same. During the head model projection some stunning visuals were stimulated, which gave another perspective to the head model. Figure 27 illustrates this scene.

Scene number nine continues to use 3D Quad Distorts as the back screen projection surface. This scene, contrary to the previous one, uses all five 3D Quad Distorts because the visuals of this scene are in full width and the optical illusion of depth can be achieved by using all the surfaces. Back screen visuals for this scene were created around the idea of stimulating a moving wall. Cinema 4D, After Effects and Isadora were used to create back screen visuals and the head model visuals were achieved by using Isadora alone.

For the back screen visuals, a landscape was first created in Cinema 4D. Next, having chosen the right properties of the landscape (depth, furrows, sea level etc.) a random object was added to the landscape. The random object was used to make a random animation of the landscape attributes. A cel renderer setting was added in this file to add a grid to the landscape. Eventually, in Cinema 4D the mesh was changed to triangular, so the landscape now looked like it was created with many triangles in constant movement (because of the random object). In order to create two new alpha layers for the scene, After Effects is used. These two new layers were created to stimulate the optical illusion. The first layer contains a number of rectangles, which are animated to move diagonally from one corner to the other one while the second layer contains a number of circles, which are animated to grow in diameter. Then, in the second layer a repeater and a merge path are added, so now when the second layer shapes face the shapes from the first layer the merging path will vanish and the background layer (layer created in Cinema 4D) will be shown (figure 28 elaborates the idea of the merging path). Thus, when this effect is applied, the illusion that this layer creates and the triangles that are in constant movement stimulate the idea of the moving wall.

FIGURE 28: MARGE PATH CREATED IN AFTER EFFECTS

When everything was finished, the video was rendered in After Effects and then imported in Isadora. In Isadora an actor named LumaCycle was added for improving colours, defining the colour positions and adding shades to the video. Another characteristic of this scene is that the back screen optical illusion of depth changes in a specific time. So from the view with depth (when five quads are used for projection) the front wall starts moving forward until it appears as only one full-screen projection surface. Therefore, this scene has the double effect of a moving wall to begin with,

when each wall stimulates the individual triangle movement and also the complete depth point of view movement.

FIGURE 29: SCENE NUMBER NINE WITH OPTICAL ILLUSION THROUGH ALPHA LAYERS

Head model visuals are created in Isadora alone by using four different actors and two videos. The first video used in this scene was bought from the Internet and the second video was created in Isadora by using particles (as with the two videos mentioned earlier). Next, the 'Image Tile' actor was used to combine these two videos. This actor uses two video inputs to display a video in the form of tiles with varying brightness. However, the video -- before being used as an input of this actor -- was first affected by the Glow actor. Then the output of the Image Tile actor was used as an input to the HSL Adjust actor for colour correction (this actor is also used to give audience control over projected colours). In addition, a 'Difference' actor was used to create an effect based on the differences of the current and the previous frame. Figure 29 shows how this scene looks.

The tenth scene was created around the idea of vortex. This scene was created completely in Isadora. The snow-like video, created earlier in Isadora, was used in this scene as a background video and another video was used to create visuals for the head model. This scene tries to create a visual illusion by using visual displacement on the head model. To create the vortex-like visual for the back screen, SpiralBlur, Motion Blur and FishEye actors are used. The SpiralBlur actor is the main actor in this scene because it creates blurriness in a circular way and, by adding Motion Blur actor, a vortex visual was stimulated from the snow video. The FishEye actor improves this scene by creating an ultra wide angle for the scene on some specific occasions (e.g. when the head starts to move in the $-z$ -axis).

The main actor for the head model is Kaleidoscope, who was used also in scene number seven. Furthermore, the actors Glow and SprialBlur are also used in this scene. Finally, the last actor is a new actor called Solarize, who is used to reverse the colour tones. The visuals of the head model in this scene look like the tribal face paintings used by some civilisations. The main characteristic of this visual scene is the illusion, which is created when the vortex swallows the head model and gives the

impression that the real physical object is swallowed and is moving in space. Figure 30 illustrates this visual scene.

FIGURE 30: SCENE NUMBER TEN VORTEX-LIKE VISUALS

Scene number eleven is created in Cinema 4d and Isadora. This scene is created around the idea of space movement. The idea is implemented by simulating the movement of the back screen visuals. In Cinema 4D the scene is created with 2 cubes that will stimulate the walls and two plates that will cover the empty spaces at the top and bottom of the scene. Cubes that stimulate the walls in the beginning will look like a flat wall, and over time, opposite sides of the walls will start to move forward and create a corner. Next, an Atom Array object is created and inside this object a Platonic object is added. Using this method, the surfaces of the platonic object have been eliminated and only the lines have remained visible. Inside this new object a volumetric light is added, and the object now looks like a cool, shiny geometric shape. This shape is hidden in the beginning and when the walls in the scene take the corner shape this shiny object will move from the top to the middle of the scene. At this point, the head model will start to move up from the bottom until it reaches the same level as the shiny object.

The head model for this scene, as in all other scenes, is fully created with Isadora. The head model was created to feature an outer glow much like the objects that were created earlier in Cinema 4D. To achieve this idea of outer glow, the head model of this scene has a glowing gold texture and this outer glow is then projected on the back screen. To create this outer glow and the gold colour for the model, the actors 3D Renderer, Bloom, Chromium and two video players are used. 3D Renderer is used to render the head model in full width and not only the model. Thus, it was possible to put the glow around the model. By combining attributes from the Bloom and Chromium actors, the glow and the gold colour were created. After some time, the object that was created earlier in Cinema 4D has an effect like an explosion and seven similar objects, but smaller in size, are created. The idea of this scene is to create a spacial illusion by combining flying shiny objects with the glowing head model and a back screen movement. Figure 31 can be helpful to create the idea for the scene.

FIGURE 31: ELEVENTH SCENE WITH THE BACK SCREEN MOVEMENT AND SHINY OBJECTS

The last scene is created in such a way that the audience will recognize that the end of the performance is coming. At first, this scene will start from the previous scene but now the movement of the back wall will go even further by giving the impression that the walls are being closed (merging) somehow. To support this stimulation, the head model, which looks like it is in the front of the wall, will start to get ‘squeezed’ with the walls, which will create the optical illusion. Also, the objects that were created in cinema 4D will start to disappear when the walls start to merge. When the walls do finally merge, the scene will be black and the snow-like video that was used in the beginning will be used again. In addition, in the end, as with the beginning, the snow-like video will start to narrow in width until it disappears. With this scene, illustrated in Figure 32, the visual performance will also be finished.

FIGURE 32: LAST SCENE CLOSING THE PERFORMANCE

All these scenes elaborated above are created in one Isadora scene. Classification of the scenes is created just to make the understanding of the performance simpler. Therefore, while in Isadora a large scene is screened and the performance continues without stopping, in most of the cases one scene is connected with the other one, so there is a flow in the performance. Before closing this section, in order to clarify the idea of how the Isadora actors are connected and how they work, we show some illustrations in figure 33, while these patches that are shown are only half of the patches that were used.

FIGURE 33: SOME PATCHES FROM THE ISADORA

CALIBRATION

The process of calibration that is used in this project is quite flexible and is one of the strong points of this project. What makes the calibration of this project unique compared to other projection-mapping projects is the possibility to adjust calibration for every kind of situation. Therefore, there is not a fixed place where the projector should be placed and where the head should stay. Isadora is the reason why this calibration is so flexible. As was mentioned earlier, the head model is imported in Isadora and then a 3D Player is used to project the model. This actor, as is shown in figure 33 a), provides the possibility to manipulate where the model should be placed in the global coordinates (x, y and z translate), the possibility to manipulate the rotations (x, y and z rotation) and the possibility to change the scale. Thus, by using these attributes, it is possible to calibrate the projection in a way that will mask the head model.

However, the problem of calibration in this case was related to the lack of projectors. In this project, a case projector was placed in a lower position compared to the head model. Therefore, mapping should be achieved from the projector's point of view.

However, logically, if we see an object from below it has a different perspective than from the front. In order to achieve the mapping of the head model calibration in Isadora it should be fixed from that point of view. To achieve this mapping, the model in Isadora was rotated in the $-x$ axis (see figure 33 b)). For this reason, the head model visuals, from the audience point of view, will have a lower cover (a slight bit of the upper part of the head is not covered with visuals). But now when the visuals of the back screen are projected, they will start from the point where the head model visuals stop, which means that they will start from that part of the head that is not covered. However, from the projector point of view, the visuals look perfectly aligned.

FIGURE 34: 3D PALYER ACTOR AND HOW PROJECTOR SEES THE HEAD FROM THE LOWER POSITION

TESTING, PROBLEMS AND DIFFICULTIES

When the project was finished the final step was to test the project. This performance, which was held in the very end, has shown also some problems that were not thought before. Two main problems were occurred in the final performance.

Physical head model during the time when only the back screen visuals were shown was always visible. This problem has caused that many optical illusion effects not to be stimulated because the audience was always aware that the head is staying there. This problem can be improved but maybe not completely solved. If the colours of the back screen and the head model would have a strong black colour not dark grey than visibility of the head would be decreased. But because of the projector light the head would again be visible because the light would indirectly illuminate the head even if visuals were not projected in it.

Second problem was related with the displacement of the head visuals. Because in the visuals part the head model is moved in the space the displacement of the head visuals were obvious (i.e. if the head was moved in the $-z$ -axis than). Even sometimes the visuals of the screen when were projected in the head they were getting deformed because the head model was in different physical shape compared to what it was supposed (flat surface). Figure 35 shows some images of the final performance where the problems were appeared.

FIGURE 35: PROBLEMS OF THE PROJECT DURING THE PERFORMANCE (a) HEAD BEING VISIBLE WHEN IT WAS NOT SUPPOSED TO BE AND (b) DISPLACEMENT OF THE VISUALS IN THE HEAD PHYSICAL OBJECT

Also During the project development, not everything has gone as smoothly as expected. But the difficulties that were faced during the development have been used as important inputs in the research. The first difficulty faced was recognising the turntable position changes. The second difficulty was the unsuitability of creating head model animation with Cinema 4D.

However, the most difficult part was keeping track of the turntable (head model) rotations. This difficulty, on the other hand, was an integral part of this research paper, as was noted above. In order to achieve the correct tracking of the head model, many solutions were tried, but the first idea was to create a special turntable for this project. The process of creating this turntable was very clear: the turntable was supposed to be built with a stepper motor and the motor was supposed to be controlled with Arduino. With this idea, tracking the movement of the stepper motor would not be a problem, but the problem was how much weight would the stepper motors hold. At this point the head model was not yet created, so the weight was unknown. The idea of using the gearbox was possible but then the process would be much more complicated. Therefore, it was decided to buy a turntable that could rotate heavy weights.

When the turntable was purchased we discovered that the motor used was an AC synchronous motor, which operates with 240VAC and is fused with 5Amps. Controlling this kind of AC motor with Arduino is almost impossible and, even if it can be controlled, the risk of fatality is quite high due to the voltages that are operated (240VAC). Another problem with this turntable that contributed to its unsuitability for Arduino control was that this motor had two cores, which were controlling both clock wise and counter clockwise rotations. This meant that one very dangerous attribute was added, because if in the case where both cores of the motor would

receive voltage input, unexpected things could happen. Therefore, at this point it was decided not to mess with the motor at all but to count the rotation from the real physical object (from outside).

There were some ideas as how to count rotations with different sensors such as magnetic sensors or light sensors. However, magnetic sensors were inappropriate because of the impossibility to be precise and mount the magnets in small degrees around the turntable. Furthermore, using light sensors was a good idea -- until a certain point. For these sensors, the decision was made to use the same process as the rotary encoders use (the process is explained in the section of hardware implementation). Thus, it was necessary to build an encoder wheel (the wheel with white and black strips) in the bottom of the turntable plate. However, the problem here was that this turntable plate was static and it was impossible to add the encoder wheel under the plate. Therefore, the final idea that was eventually implemented was to use ready rotary encoders, the process which is explained earlier in this paper.

The second difficulty that had a direct influence on how and what the visuals would be created was the unsuitability of using Cinema 4D to create the visuals of the head model. Before the project began, it was thought that the visuals of the back screen and the head model would be created in a way that they will interact with each other. Even though some interactions were realised between these visuals those interactions would be improved by using Cinema 4D.

The difficulty here was that Cinema 4D does not support live rendering so the animations would be created one time and then the same animation would be used over and over again. For example, if an animation was created where the head would be in the front position and a projector would be at a certain distance from the head model, then this animation can be used only for that distance and when the head is on front. Thus, the independency of making a performance in different places would be limited because now calibration is done some hours before the performance and it does not meter the distance of the projector with the screen or any other position attribute. So the project can be demounted easily and then sent to another place and within a couple of hours all would be ready. In other projection mapping this is impossible because they use only static visuals with a static calibration.

Moreover, the performance, should the Cinema 4D be used, would have a negative influence in terms of audience interaction. This is because, in those moments when the visuals of the head model are to be shown, the audience could not rotate the head, since the animation and the physical object would be displaced. One solution would be to create the animation for each position of the head model, which means to create 360 animations. But this solution is clearly impossible because the time that would be needed to do all of these animations -- and also many other attributes that are created in Isadora to give audience control in performance -- would be lost. Finally, the last problem would be that the computer that is currently being used would have great

difficulty in processing that number of videos during the head rotation, leading to the possibility of losing calibration during the performance.

FINDINGS AND FURTHER WORK

By being focused on the process of achieving the aim of this project, which was to project visuals in an audience controlled live mapped surface, some interesting things have been found. First, it can be concluded that mapping physical objects in real time is a feasible process. Secondly, the findings indicate that if the physical object has a certain depth, the use of more than one projector is necessary. Finally, the findings suggest that one projector is not enough to project two physical objects if they are placed in the same line.

The process of creating live projection mapping can be achieved by combining hardware and software solutions. First, it is recommended to have an exact 3D model of the object that is going to be mapped. This can be achieved in many ways. For example, if the object that is going to be used for projection is going to be built from the beginning, as in this project case, it is preferable to create the object first in any 3D software, since in this way the same model can be used for mapping and also for building the physical object. However, if the object that is going to be mapped already exists, then by taking pictures of the model from different angles and from the same distance, a three-dimensional photo model can be created. These pictures can then be used to recreate the model in the 3D structure (by importing in any 3D software and than using the lines on the picture to draw the model). The last solution is to use 3D scanners. These scanners are becoming more and more popular for the purpose of creating 3D models from real physical objects. With these scanners, any object can be recreated in a three-dimensional model by just using the scanner and rotating the object to scan all of the surfaces.

Once the 3D model of the physical object that is going to be mapped exists then different sensors can be used to track any changes that the physical model is making in his projection surface. As in this project's case, by using outer sensors rotations are detected, but any kind of movement or change in the projection surface can be detected. Then the projection surface changes of the physical object should influence changes on the 3D model of the projected object. For achieving these changes in the 3D model live, render software should be used. Fortunately, nowadays many types of this kind of software exists in the market.

The second finding of this project suggests that if the physical object that is going to be projected has a depth of more than 10 cm, it is preferable to have at least 2 projectors. This recommendation stands because, if only one projector is used in front of the object, the viewpoint is limited in terms of maximum capacity. If in this case the audience moves from the point of view, pixels stretches would be seen. Using two or more projectors would not only limit the pixels stretches but would make the point

of view much wider. Depending on the size of the object and the number of the projectors, the point of view can be increased to its maximum. Thus, from every angle the audience would have a perfect viewpoint. However, if only one projector is used, as in this project, only one viewpoint exists. Moreover, this viewpoint is hard to access because it is in the same line as the projector eye. So the best view point of projection mapping with only one projector is around the projector's eye, which is quite hard to be achieved because it is impossible to put the audience near the projector as it will interfere with their view.

The third finding of this project is also related to the usage of more than one projector. This finding concludes that if more than one surface is used and these surfaces are placed in the same line as projector, then the surface, which is behind the first surface will have black shadows and it will be impossible to cover that surface completely because the first surface will not allow it. For example, if we consider this project, we find the back screen is not covered in the places when the head model is in front of it. Thus, if the audience enter to the side of the back screen, they would see a black model of the head in the model of it, as the projector could not light that place. Furthermore, if only one projector is used, then the back screen visuals could possibly be projected in the head model should the projector not be placed completely in a straight line with head model.

These findings offer a clear recommendation of how this project can be improved in the future. By using two projectors for the head model and a separate projector for the back screen, the viewpoint can be increased to a high level. In addition, by increasing the viewpoint, the audience's freedom of movement would also be increased. This process would require using different techniques of projection. One projector would be placed in the upper part of the left side and the second projector would be placed in the lower part of the right side. Now the head model would have a perfect cover. However, these two projectors would need to be calibrated in such a way that none of them would project in the area of the other projector. In addition, the projector of the back screen could be placed in the centre-top part of the back screen or in the bottom-centre part of the screen. This would increase the number of people who could see the performance and none of the projectors would interfere with their view.

In the future, this project can also improve audience interaction. Since only two buttons are now used for interaction, in the future a midi controller can be used to achieve much more interaction. Using this method, the audience would have the possibility to control visuals to a much higher level, and maybe even build them on their own. A midi controller can be used to add special effects, to change scenes or combine the effects and rotate the head. More audience interaction can be achieved by also using space sensors such as 'kinect' whence the movement of the audience would influence visuals. Adding a draw pad connecting it with Processing and then connecting Processing with Isadora can give the audience the possibility to draw visuals in real time for projection. Giving the audience the potential to control the

visuals with their phones would increase the values of this project. Multi users could interact in the same time, which would make the project quite interesting.

In future work this project could improve the process of live mapping by using additional movements for the physical head model rather than just rotations. Thus, if the x, y and z-axis of the object could also be controlled, the possibility of creating optical illusions would be significantly increased. In order to achieve this special mechanical structure, four motors can be used, where each movement and the rotation would be controlled with a separate motor. Through using this idea, both audience interaction and the optical illusion would be improved considerably.

CONCLUSION

This project was created in order to stimulate an optical illusion by using the technique of live render projection mapping. Furthermore, the audience is placed at the centre of the project by giving them the opportunity to change and manipulate the projected surface. A planar surface and a three-dimensional head model are used as a projected surface. The planar surface is used as a background screen for the head model so the head model is mapped and visuals are then projected independently onto the back screen and in the head model. Furthermore, the audience rotates the head model, which means that the audience have directly controlled the surface that was mapped.

This paper has all the necessary information to understand the idea of the project and also the process of how this project was built. This project tries to give new perspective to static projection mapping and achieve maximum audience engagement.

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